

JURIDICAL SCIENCES

EVIDENCE EVALUATION ACTIVITY OF THE COURTS AND ITS CRIMINALISTIC ASPECTS

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ABSTRACT

The article elaborates the problems of evaluating the results obtained by the courts during the preliminary investigation and the issues determining the relationship between the authenticity of the cases determined in the case and the decisions made regarding them. While examining the case materials presented by the preliminary investigation and the evidence collected by the court, the evaluation processes and criminalistic aspects were studied and explained both in terms of determining the truth of the committed crime in terms of legally significant circumstances, and in terms of the correctness of the chosen path and the methods and methods of obtaining evidence. Here, the expert research conducted during the preliminary investigation, the reliability of the evidence based on it and the evaluation of the legality of the prepared expert opinions, the verification of compliance with the procedural rules, the experimental methods that determine the reliability and legality of the obtained data and results have been scientifically investigated. In any case, the stages of the criminal process, arising from the tasks of the criminal proceedings and the goals of justice, differ in terms of the participants of the criminal-procedural relations, the procedural actions performed and the decisions made, and constitute a certain system. Also, the opinions of scientists who have conducted research in this field in the world experience and the obtained results have been studied and examples have been shown.

Keywords: forensic evidence, criminalistic aspect, procedural rule, reliability of evidence, evaluation activity, research method, evaluation of evidence.

In the context of the successive improvement of legal relations aimed at the implementation of judicial reforms, the decisive determination of the role of the court in the criminal process is considered a very actual issue. In Part I of Article 125 of Chapter VII of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Judicial Power, it is unequivocally declared that only courts are implemented by judicial judgement [1, p. 47].

However, the criminal process has a distinctive feature that affects the realization of the relevant constitutional principles, which is its being staged. That is, we are talking about the division of criminal-procedural activity into separate stages. In its turn, the stages of the criminal process, in any case, arising from the tasks of criminal proceedings and the goals of justice, differ in terms of the participants of criminal-procedural relations, the procedural actions performed and the decisions made, and constitute a certain system, in which each stage is defined in advance, with other stages exists closely and mutually.

Here, the previous stage lays the groundwork for the next stage, and that stage, along with other issues, necessarily resolves the legality and validity of its creation. In other words, it evaluates the actions and decisions taken at the previous stage and carries out the inspection. It should also be noted that the authority to conduct criminal proceedings belongs to individual officials or bodies, which is considered very important in

such a system of stages. Accordingly, control over the activities of "predecessors" can be carried out independently, which maximizes the possibility of a legal, reasonable and fair resolution of the final decision on the criminal case.

It is not necessary for every criminal case to go through all the stages of the process and reach the court investigation, which ends with the verdict, that is, the solution of the issue can be resolved before the court during the preliminary investigation proceedings. In this case, of course, it will not be about justice in a criminal case. However, all decisions made in the criminal process must meet the same set requirements, the foremost of which are legal, reasonable and fair principles.

In order to achieve this result, a number of procedural powers have been applied, such as conducting a preliminary investigation and supervising the activity of the prosecutor's office before the case enters the court. Recently, the jurisdiction of the court in this area, that is, in the area of judicial control, has been expanding.

In any case, the realization of the requirements of the criminal-procedural legislation manifests itself in the activity of proving the circumstances necessary for the adoption of one or another decision on a criminal case. Therefore, in this article, the concept of evaluation of evidence is taken as an element of the evidentiary process, and the criteria that form its basis are examined

in detail. In general, the word evaluation in linguistics is understood both as an assessment based on the verb to evaluate, to rate, and to assess, and as an opinion, a given review, about the qualities and values of something or someone. Apparently, the etymology of the word used as a legal term should reflect both the specific activity and the joint nature of its result. In the procedural literature, the majority of authors imagine the evaluation of evidence as a logical thinking activity aimed at determining the possibility, relevance, importance and truth of each piece of evidence for the purpose of determining the circumstances that must be proven in a criminal case by the person or persons conducting the investigation, the prosecutor and the court.

Such an approach seems unilateral not only from the etymological, but also from the legal-procedural point of view. The main legal burden of the concept of evidence evaluation is that any decisions on the case are made based on its results in the criminal process. It is precisely this content aspect of the evaluation of evidence that is not given enough attention in the above-mentioned issues. In other words, the assessment of evidence can act as a foundation, factual basis, ground for every decision, as rightly noted by scientists such as R.S. Belkin [2], G.M. Minkovski [3], P.A. Lupinskaya [4] and other researchers.

For example, P.A. Lupinskaya considers the two stages of legal decision-making to be a part of the first one, noting the determination of the factual circumstances for decision-making and the decision-making on any action, behavior [4, pp. 34-35].

Developing this position and analyzing the structure of criminal-procedural evidence, Z.Z. Zinatullin considers it as a set of elements (five elements), from which "evaluation of available means of evidence (evidence, their source, methods of acquisition and use)" and mentions "the formation and justification of reliable results and decisions on the case" as independent elements [5, p.18].

A.A. Davletov's opinion on this is also interesting. He believes that the evaluation activity in the criminal process cannot be taken simply as an evaluation of the evidence, as in the investigation of the criminal case, not only the evidence, but also the circumstances and facts are evaluated [6, pp. 76-78].

Indeed, it is very difficult to establish a clear and definite distance between the individual elements of proof. However, it is often (except in exceptional cases) incorrect that the possibilities of proof result in two stages, the collection and evaluation of evidence. Compliance with the articles of collection of evidence, checking of evidence and evaluation of evidence in the evidence chapter of the current Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan results from the relevance of the essence of the process [7, p. 166-167]. Evidence in criminal cases is a unique and at the same time multi-faceted, universal activity, which means that various components appear and arise during the evidence. Evaluation of evidence takes a special place in this process. Thus, it is practically closely linked with other elements of proof, it goes through the process of proof and forms the basis of the next stages for the investigation of business cases. For example, during the

interrogation, the victim informs the investigator or the court about the witnesses of the crime.

Here, the interrogating body feels the need to make a decision to interrogate the persons whose names are mentioned in the list by verbally evaluating the obtained information. Of course, the practical implementation of the decision will happen a little later, even after the obtained information is verified. However, the necessity of the decision to be made in essence arises at the same time as obtaining relevant evidentiary information.

According to the mentioned considerations, XV chapter called "Proving" was included in the Criminal Procedure Code, in which, apart from the articles dedicated to the collection and evaluation of evidence, a separate article under the heading "Evidence verification" was applied [7, p.163-167]. Such a proposal to improve procedural legislation is very reasonable and legitimate, but somewhat incomplete. For example, paragraph 138.1 of Article 138 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Azerbaijan states that proof "consists of obtaining, checking and evaluating evidence for the purpose of determining circumstances that are important for the legal, reasonable and fair resolution of the charge." [7, p.163].

Accordingly, in the subsequent articles, the issue of the relationship between the proof and the resolution of the case, that is, the adoption of various decisions on the basis of it, should be approached more carefully and a precise provision should be defined.

In this regard, we think that the norms characterizing the decision-making process should be included in the criminal-procedural code as a logical conclusion of the evidence chapter. We believe that the relevant article may contain the following content:

1. The court, prosecutor, investigator, and investigative body carry out their activities in accordance with the legal decisions made only on the basis of the evidence in the case, to the extent provided for in this Code.

2. Checked and properly evaluated evidence is the only basis for making a legal, reasonable and fair decision on the case.

3. The decision can be written or oral.

The written decision is reflected in a separate document or part of it, or in a relevant document, which justifies and expresses the decision adopted in the manner prescribed by law. The procedural form of such decisions can be in the form of documents such as judgment, indictment, decision, order, presentation, sanction, approval and consent.

Making an oral decision is understood as the execution of any procedural action and the presence of a document reflecting its course and content in the work materials.

Decisions made in the criminal case enter into legal force immediately, within the period indicated by the law or during the sanction period, and their implementation is considered mandatory by all bodies, officials and citizens. Instead of the decisions, the responsibility determined by the law is provided for whether they are executed or not.

Thus, discussing the importance and place of evidence evaluation in the criminal process for solving the case, we conclude that it is related to procedural decision-making. The next stage of decision-making is its implementation, that is, the execution of specific actions that allow obtaining new evidence. Their assessment, in its turn, will lead to the adoption and implementation of new decisions. It can be noted that there is a certain interaction between all elements of this chain in cases of achieving the goals of criminal proceedings and ensuring the rights of process participants.

The result obtained as a result of the evaluation activity is revealed through the prism of the implemented actions and new results obtained. In this case, it is also very natural that flaws in the assessment phase, which is fundamental, will lead to wrong decisions, illegal actions or negative consequences.

From this, it is important to conclude how the collected evidence is evaluated can be judged on the criminal case materials, first of all on the decisions made based on them. That is, in other words, it is possible to express an opinion or evaluate the results of the criminal-procedural activities of specific officials, including the evaluation of the evidence collected by them. This, as mentioned above, allows the court to supervise the activities of the "predecessors", including the investigative bodies.

According to this provision, there is a need to analyze the parameters characterizing the evaluation of evidence in the criminal process, and therefore to evaluate the quality of the procedural activity. In the literature, the terms "criterion", "requirement", and rarely "properties" or "principles" are used for this.

It is considered more logical to refer to the etymology of the mentioned terms so that there is no change or repetition in their use. So, the sign, the measure taken as the basis for evaluating an issue that is a criterion; a rule requiring strict and careful behavior; unquestioningly, necessarily subordinate; Terms are meant as a set of norms and conditions for the future of something.

The term we use here is more appropriate for the problem we are trying to solve in the article. It is also related to the intrinsic properties of the evaluation of evidence. Demand has generalization content and is a slightly higher term in terms of meaning. In essence, we can say that the evaluation criteria are requirements. Since we are talking about analysis and legal matter in the legal field, the basic requirements for the evaluation of evidence, the decisions made, and their implementation are reflected in the laws.

As for the terms property and principle, they mean, respectively, a distinctive feature of something and the basic, starting premise of any theory, teaching; means the quality, sign, ability that characterizes or reflects the main activity. Apparently, the etymological meaning of these words corresponds more to the characteristics of other legal manifestations related to the evaluation of evidence, that is, to its content. Thus, we will assume here that the evaluation of evidence is based on the use of certain criteria. However, although a group of scientists in the world practice call this set of criteria differently, they are not unambiguously characterized in the legal literature.

Regarding these, A.M. Larin notes that the choice of evaluation criteria of law enforcement activity should be related to problematic, unresolved issues [8, pp. 113-115].

In the article, we do not claim a definitive solution to this issue, but we want to propose the evaluation activity as evidence evaluation criteria, and therefore, we want to try to show the most important signs that can be used by the court in the evaluation of preliminary investigation materials. We believe that here it would be more correct to study the principle of harmonizing the evaluation criteria of the evidence. Indeed, the evidentiary process in a criminal case is aimed at establishing the truth. The evaluation of the evidence is very close to the fact of reaching the truth in the case, as it acts as the final stage of the proof process with the necessary decisions being made later. The concept of truth in the criminal process and the possibilities of achieving it are considered to be one of the most controversial issues in the legal references. Touching the aspects related to the evaluation of evidence and criminal case materials, without deeply interfering with the essence of theoretical disputes, characterizes the main features of the problem.

In the theory of cognitive philosophy, which is the basis of the theory of evidence in the criminal process, truth is generally defined as an adequate reflection of reality by the subject, imagining it as it is regardless of thinking. Objective truth is cognitive content independent of humanity. Truth is the correspondence of perception to the object, and the object to its own understanding. From this we can conclude that objective truth is subjective in terms of form, so it depends on how it is determined in the cognitive process and how the laws of logical thinking are followed.

By changing epistemological approaches to the concept of truth, a group of scientists explain its objective nature and the possibilities of its determination in criminal proceedings in different ways. Sufficient attention has been paid to the mentioned problem-issue, but this issue is of great importance in the discussion of the Criminal Procedure Code. In the legal references, different and sometimes conflicting opinions are expressed about the evaluation of evidence.

The denial of objective truth and the possibility of its achievement in judicial activity was previously characteristic of jurisprudence. Until the 60s of the last century, the truth was practically denied in the criminal process, and procedural decisions were made on the basis of probable opinions. In the world experience, we can see that a number of scientists support such ideas.

For example, S.A. Golunski wrote: "Determining the truth is not the goal of the criminal process. The process is not a scientific-research activity. The objectives of the process are listed in Article 2 of the Basics of Criminal Procedure, and it is no coincidence that the determination of the truth is not among them" [9, p. 138-139].

When looking at the world experience, the prevailing position in the criminal procedural science is that the preliminary investigation bodies and courts not only do not determine the truth, but also to determine the truth in each criminal case, therefore, to come to the

correct conclusion about the legally significant circumstances of the crime and make legal decisions that they consider themselves a debt. One of such researchers is P.F. Pashkevich, who devoted a large number of scientific works to the problem of determining the truth in the criminal process. It does not constitute an exception to the general rule of determining the truth in the criminal process and is carried out according to the laws of general human cognitive activity. He emphasizes that it is necessary to accept the determination of the truth in a criminal case as a special case of cognition [10, p.97-100].

However, different opinions about the concept of truth have been put forward in the procedural references.

For example, according to the opinion put forward by M.S. Strogovich, the material truth in the criminal process fully corresponds to the objective facts of the investigation and court results [11, pp. 56-57].

Z.Z. Zinatulli also has interesting ideas about the problem. He believes that the concept of objective truth "understands whether the results of investigation, prosecutor's office and judicial authorities on the investigated and solved criminal case have established facts and their legally significant properties, the relevance of the degree of legal responsibility of the perpetrator to the real reality." At this time, it is possible to achieve the truth in the criminal process only if all its grounds, evidence and all the results of the case, that is, the decisions, reflect the objective reality and reflect the truth [5, p.21].

As it can be seen, in the mentioned definition, the idea about the relationship between the determination of the truth in a criminal case and the adoption of procedural decisions based on it is evident, which is fully consistent with the practical provision of the most important criterion of truth in criminal proceedings.

Of course, truth criteria and evidence evaluation criteria are not the same thing. As a result of the evaluation of the evidence, real decisions are made on the basis of the truth of the case. That is, the second derives from the first.

Criminal procedural laws provide only one method of arriving at the truth in criminal cases. Accordingly, the main purpose of the evaluation of the evidence, which is its constituent element, also carries out the process of determining the truth [15].

As mentioned, recently, scientific research on the problems of determining the truth in the criminal process has become more active. This is also related to the creation of the jury court, in which the procedural rules for the resolution of cases in these courts create a basis for reconsidering the issues of determining the truth and the necessity of character in the criminal process [13]. Here, there are attempts to return the positions that prevailed earlier to determine the objective truth in the criminal case and make decisions on the basis of possible information.

V.S. Balakshin believes that the objective truth is a fiction, more precisely, the criminal code is a legal fiction that allows you to use it for sentencing, so its maintenance as a tool of the criminal process implies that the procedural truth comes first [12, pp. 312-314].

Considering that the issue we are trying to study in the article is the assessment of the results of the preliminary investigation bodies by the court and the problems of its criminalistic aspects, it is very important to note that there is a connection between the authenticity of the cases determined in the case and the decisions made regarding them. From this point of view, it can be noted the necessity of forming objective, true results of the bodies that carry out criminal proceedings. Therefore, when examining the case materials presented by the preliminary investigation and the collected evidence, the court should evaluate them both in terms of determining the truth about the legally significant circumstances of the committed crime, and in terms of the correctness of the chosen path and the methods and ways of obtaining evidence.

The last provision requires a special position in the selection of evaluation criteria of formal activity results with the requirements of the non-procedural, i.e., criminal-procedural law. There is no doubt that such activity does not exist. Because the law establishes special rules for preliminary investigation proceedings, specifically for investigative actions. However, the law does not have the power to regulate all possible numerous cases arising in specific criminal cases in the criminal process. Therefore, in this case, the advisory regulations come into force, and these provisions do not have a mandatory normative character. All these are generally accepted rules in legal practice. This primarily refers to forensic expert recommendations based on law enforcement experience [14].

However, it can be concluded that the evaluation of any activity can be based on the obtained result. Its authenticity testifies to the effectiveness and quality of the path chosen for it. Indeed, the criterion of truth is experience. However, there are specific points in the field of criminal-procedural activity, the consideration of which leads to the conclusion that there are personality criteria in the evaluation of both the evidence collected in the case and the procedural decisions made based on them.

In any case, the evaluation analysis of work materials in terms of legality is carried out both in terms of the adopted decisions and in terms of the process of their implementation. In this regard, the following are considered the most important signs of compliance with legality requirements:

1. Who should take a specific decision and who should implement it, whether they have the appropriate powers for this;

2. Whether or not the rules on procedural terms are followed or the adoption and implementation of the relevant decision in a timely manner;

3. Whether or not that decision is drawn up in the necessary procedural form;

4. Whether the provisions of the law guaranteeing the rights of process participants are observed at the stages of decision adoption and its execution;

5. Whether or not procedural rules are followed when carrying out a specific action and drawing up its results;

6. Execution of mandatory sequential actions, etc.

Here, the court, while evaluating the legality of the expertise research conducted during the preliminary investigation and the expert opinion drawn up in terms of legality, must reconcile the related case materials with the norms of the criminal-procedural legislation regulating the rules of expertise, the law "On the activity of judicial expertise" and the instructions for conducting expertise. The choice of the expert's research method and methodology and the determination of the expertise, ensuring the rights of the accused person (persons), obtaining samples for comparative research, their quality and degree of reliability, the period of execution of the expertise and the credibility of the evidence on which it is based, the content of the expert's opinion, its presentation to the accuser, solving the issues of appointment of additional or repeated expertises and other issues should be kept in mind.

After the comprehensive evaluation of the mentioned relevant materials, the court can consider the legality of both the implementation of the procedural activity and the information obtained as a result of it.

Thus, the legal thinking and experience of the court or the judge can have a professional legal result regarding the directions of the processes performed both in the evaluation of the evidence and in the evaluation of the results of the procedural activity.

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